

Nepal's Educational System and its Impact on Policy and Governance: A Review

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Abstract

To review Nepal Government policy and education governance.

Method: The researcher provides a thorough review of the research findings that have been published at the national and international levels. To analyse articles about policy and governance-related topics and combine the data, the researcher employed a scientific review technique called meta-analysis. Collecting research papers, reports, and data and conducting a comprehensive assessment in conjunction with thorough archival analysis would be the methods used for the scientific evaluation in a systematic way.

Finding: In Nepal, the constitution of 2015 provides for up to 12 years of free education in public schools. More than 11 universities have opened in Nepal, including Tribhuvan University (formerly the University of Nepal), Mahendra Sanskrit University, Purbanchal University, Lumbini Buddhist University (LBU), Agriculture and Forestry University (AFU), Mid-Western University (MWU), Far-Western University (FWU), Nepal Open University (NOU), and Rajarshi Janak University (RJU), Pradesh University, Birgunj, Pokhara University.

Recommendation: The Nepalese government offers three different kinds of education in Nepal, which prepares students for employment or entrepreneurship. First, secondary level education (up to the 12 pass). Give practical skills and training for market links. Secondly, mid-level (Bachelor and Master Level) human resource creation and provide opportunities for them to work in the private, public, and business sectors. Thirdly, high-level (MPhil, PhD, Post Doc, and DSc./D.Litt.) manpower production for planners, researchers, scientists, and monitoring and documentation preparation.

Free education up to the 12th grade was provided by the Nepalese government in schools at the government level. In Nepal, there are now over eleven open universities. These institutions are offering superior education. Students from technical institutes are unable to provide a quality education. Young people are better equipped to become entrepreneurs and work independently when they receive a good education and high standards. Always take into account production driven by the market and linkup production in the market since it fosters entrepreneurship and perfect education. Create workers at the basic, intermediate, and upper levels.

Keywords: review, status, policy, governance, action